

ARCHIVING LUDOLOGICAL NARRATIVES: THE PRESERVATION OF FOLK GAMES IN PUNJAB, PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to investigate how indigenous or folk games such as Gharms Ghori, Chug Chug, Pitto Gol Garam, Bandar Qilla, etc. evolved and survived through the times. The study intends to archive these games which have never been part of public discourse due to the lack of credible recorded sources. Research is conducted through focus groups, observations, field notes and personal interviews of people of various age groups. This investigation has challenged the ideas of locality, history & origin. Therefore, these games help to create a new methodology while giving shape to fresh strategies in preserving and archiving the intangible culture and alternate history from a unique perspective.

Keywords: oral history, anthropological and socio-political narratives, marginalized community of Lahore, archiving indigenous games of Punjabi culture...

INTRODUCTION

The formal aspect of this research is to address the adaptation of human behavior to the changing roles of the viewer and the viewed. The scope of the study is focused on the daily lives of ordinary people from socially marginalized groups in the outskirts of Lahore, Pakistan and the documentation of the evolution of their concept of personal and public spaces. To that effect, the critical framework hinges upon the sociocultural anthropological approach, which compares and correlates people, and their surroundings and the narratives that are being formed with the inhabitation of the said space. The research process involves visualizing such narratives through a time-based medium such as a camera, juxtaposing environs and objects of the personal significance of the group in the study. Therefore, the narratives

established through intervening in these person-to-person and person-to-object relationships, highlight their personal approach to authorship. These personalized portrayals are an attempt to gain understanding and present their lives as it is, all along playing with the idea of reversing the role of the author and subject. The video documentation encapsulates their everyday lifestyle and provides an insider's view of how each individual inhibits and exhibits themselves in front of the camera, amidst their own surroundings. They depict the idea of adapting to the role of a subject to an intrusion i.e. camera in their 'natural' environs. The narratives thus emerge naturally, blurring the boundaries of subject and object by making the identity of the author fluctuate between the two. Such

encounters occur, when the process of documenting narratives initiates without a preconceived plan of action which emancipates the cameraman as an author, thus cooperating with multiple views of everyday life. The aim of this study is not to make new information or to depict themes of voyeurism in the existing information but to highlight the alternate interpretations of the banality of people in spaces, which provokes the revision of the public and private in order to transform perceptions about the marginalized community.

The study will take an interdisciplinary approach in investigating the origins and evolution of local/folk games (*lok khed*) of Lahore such as *Gharmas / Kamas Ghori, Chug Chug, Kaenchay, Bandar Qila, Pito Gol Garam*, etc. which has now rendered almost absent from public memory. These games were chosen as a mode of investigation primarily because of the fact that these games have indefinite/ undefined, shifting origins since they have been transmitted through oral history.

Recorded history began with the invention of writing, over time new ways of recording history were invented with the advancement of technology. New archiving sources and determinants for history are audio recordings, photography and various visual mediums. More recently, the advent of the World Wide Web has allowed history to be recorded on the Internet. These Promethean advances and modes of documentation are the new mediums for oral history. A room for doubt in oral history remains because it is a recollection of human memory which has an element of forgetfulness. This unintentional misinformation acts like the game of Chinese whisper, as it has an incredible edge for imagination and multiple ideas of understanding. Due to the shifting origins of these games, an exciting number of possibilities emerge; such as how the socio-economic changes of the locality have affected the development and continuation of these games. At the same time, in these games, changes have been absorbed by the inclusion of terminologies and rules, resulting in social-political upheavals. For example in a game called *Bandar Qila* (Fig.1), a certain movement takes

place, while opponents are supposed to obstruct the movement of the player from point A to point B, which is (interestingly) called “Hajj”. The term “Hajj” may result from the Arabization of the current locality or a reference to the metaphysical understanding of “every day” similar to the references made in Sufi poetry. This investigation allows us to rediscover preconceived ideas of locality, histories and origins. These games become a complex set of tools and methodologies, which create fresh approaches and strategies to question the ideas of locality, identity and histories. The purpose of this study is to explore and investigate the factors that are contributing to the marginalization of traditional and folk games in Punjab, Pakistan in order to preserve the social and cultural values of our heritage which is also at stake.

The following questions have been listed down to realize the gap in the study:

- How are folk and traditional games in the outskirts of Lahore evolved, archived, and preserved social and cultural narratives?
- How did these games develop and incorporate the dominant narratives of history in Punjab and present alternate perspectives?
- What are the factors that are contributing to the endangerment of traditional games in Punjab, Pakistan?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review examined for this study was in reference to the theoretical framework and these readings have been analyzed concerning the study. This measure was taken to ensure that the component of the research question regarding the origins and archiving of folk games will be addressed and the findings from this chapter will be organized accordingly. For the following heading, relevant literature was reviewed and assessed to fill the gap in the study.

Preservation of culture through archived Folk Games

Since the beginning of Indian civilization, games have played a significant role in its society. Many of the traditional games that are played now all across the world are thought to have originated in India. These games call on coordination, strength,

endurance, speed, agility, and other physical attributes in addition to technical and tactical capabilities. Aside from this, our traditional games are less expensive and require less equipment than modern games, which has led to a rise in the popularity of traditional Indian games, especially among the working class due to a lack of provisions for obtaining sports gadgets. But for them to be effectively promoted and for Indians to be able to preserve their rich heritage, a lot more work needs to be done at the federal level.

In India, one of the most well-liked traditional sports is *kho-kho*. Many historians believe that "Run and Chase" has been adapted to become the game of *Kho-Kho*. A game called *Rathera* was played in the past on raths or chariots in Maharashtra, and it was a variation of *Kho-Kho*. "Active Chase," a key component of the Indian game *Kho Kho*—which is synonymous with the term "Game of Chase"—is believed to be a hunting activity. Saying that *Kho Kho* was a well-known sport in antiquity, even before the first mythological texts of the classical *Mahabharata*, would not be a mistake.

Furthermore, another South Asia game with its roots embedded in mythology, *Kabaddi's* origins can be traced back to prehistoric times when humans learned how to defend themselves against animals in groups or attack weaker creatures on their own or in groups to survive and obtain food. The game is compared in *Mahabharata* to a precarious scenario in which Abhimanyu, the Pandava king's successor, finds himself encircled by the enemy on all sides.

Additionally, history shows that ancient princes used the game of *Kabaddi* to demonstrate their might and woo their future wives. *Kabaddi* is primarily more popular in Asian countries, while interest in it is growing in other nations as well.

Moreover, in the South Asian context, the more "institutionalized" games had to make way for the folk games, which had existed for decades in rural Bengal. Folk games were supplanted and lost as colonial games left their impact on Calcuttans' lives in a variety of ways. The goal of the colonizers throughout their time in India was to establish a class of people who were Indian by blood and color but English by taste, manner, etiquette, and intellect. However, folk sport is an umbrella term

encompassing a wide range of indigenous sports belonging to a tribe or community that were primarily played for enjoyment, amusement, and physical and mental development of its people. Since these games were typically played and enjoyed during cultural or seasonal fairs or gatherings, they have the characteristic of being portrayed as "popular culture." The neighborhood and locality were crucial to these kinds of sports. Prior to the invention of television and cell phones, people in rural societies enjoyed a social life. If these native games and sports were an essential component of a particular rural culture, it stands to reason that when the landlords and aristocrats left their native space, they were cut off from both the games and the sports of that region. Their aim to adopt a Western lifestyle for themselves stunted the growth of these kinds of folk games in the neighborhood. Such folk games were easily patronized, at least in the native-inhabited area of Calcutta, but in the reform era, middle-class moral policing eliminated rural games and rural culture from the Bhadrakalok's way of life.

Folk sports are the opposite of modern sports: they are made-up customs supported by material rituals and immaterial myths, which the common folk participate in to display their romanticized ethnic identities. In the face of industrialization and globalization, traditional sports and games around the world are marginalizing, just like other cultural traditions. To combat these trends of cultural homogenization, UNESCO adopted the Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity in 2003. Folk sports are currently protected by UNESCO preserving policies as components of intangible cultural heritage. Rather than cultural preservation, tourism and nationalism drove the inclusion of regional folk sports on the UNESCO Representative List. The practice, prestige, and significance of folk sports were not impacted by UNESCO's revitalization, but there was an impact on the connection between the preservation of folk sports and nation-building narratives. Cultural nationalists aim to strengthen national unity through shared cultural practices, such as the adoption of national folk sports; external nationalists compete for worldwide recognition through "UNESCO status"; and folk sport, often

known as ethnosport, continues to be a symbol of ethnonational identity. This claim offers a fresh viewpoint on the idea of intangible cultural heritage and folk athletic traditions in our increasingly homogenous global village by mobilizing information across a spectrum of academic fields.

DESIGN OF THE STUDY

This is case study-based qualitative research. The plan was to archive and document the existing Punjabi games on the outskirts of Lahore i.e. Ring Road. The games were studied for their strategic elements and the players' actions were observed through semi-structured interviews and video recording of the open spaces where these games are still played.

The participants selected for this study, were of varying ages, including people in their 60s and 70s beside children to provide information regarding older cultural and traditional versions of the games. The older participants helped us forge an alternative history of the local culture and politics of Punjab. The questions were regarding the nature of these games in the older times and how they have evolved over time. The factors pertaining to the de-popularization of these games were also explored. In addition to that, the historical background and their transmission from their original version to the contemporary times were investigated in these interviews as well.

The secondary data related to the archival research of folk games was collected from online sources. Several published articles, peer-reviewed journals, web articles and published books were reviewed for this study. Keywords related to the theoretical frameworks were typed into the search engine to generate documents with concerns similar to the related research.

For empirical sources, several interviews with elderly and young people were conducted to investigate their knowledge of these games. Interviews were noted down in handwritten notes, and audio and video recordings. Similarly, the documentation of the games was made in a video format, several games were watched with an elderly guide for more clarification on the history, rules and strategies regarding those games. The analysis

of the findings was made on the basis of observing these video recordings.

The video recordings were analyzed and observed as documents for the purpose of this study. This analysis aimed to conclude if the games have been preserved in their entirety without any influence of popular culture or have evolved completely.

All the interviews conducted for this study have been structured to focus on the research question in order to explore to oral history attached to the Punjabi folkgames. The interviewees had been told the purpose statement of the research and the mode of recording the interviews (audio/video) had been approved by them. Upon their approval, video documentation of the games was recorded along with field notes for analysis that would be incorporated into the research findings.

FINDINGS

The results of this study are divided into two parts. Part one will highlight the data related to the history of Punjabi folkgames which were accumulated through interviews while the second part of this section will be the analysis of the visual documentation of the folkgames.

Part I

The data collected is suggestive of the fact that the culture preserved in folk games is largely deduced from public memory. The interviews conducted during this research are to support this conclusion.

Several interviews were conducted in total and many of the interviewees acknowledge the sense of cultural loss the region has witnessed since partition. Iqbal Bakhsh an octogenarian from Manawala, Punjab recalls how during the early years of Independence this culture had managed to maintain its hold over the public. He states that where a subtle form of Westernization was seeping the cultural landscape, the presence of 'local culture' was still felt among the country's rural population.

Another interviewee, Mukhtar Hussain, a fruit vendor from Shadman believes that our society has lost touch with its past. He blames uncontrolled commercialization and 'the worship of money' as the root cause for this cultural neglect. He states that people nowadays promote

values associated with foreign culture(s) in their attempt to imitate the socially upward Arab and European societies which are capitalistic.

Salik Bhatti, a war veteran remembers how in his youth he used to play *Gilli Danda* and *Gharmas Ghori* with his friends after school. He frowned at the thought of what he considers to be the 'devilish activities' youngsters indulge in today. He believes that our economic and technological progress has come at the cost of losing our identity. He blamed successive governments for refusing to recognize our 'own' culture.

Andleeb Zahra, a school teacher from Lahore's posh Defence locality however takes a different view of things. She believes that the cultural norms that dominated our society in older times reinforced patriarchal values and undermined women's rights. She finds it very disturbing women were excluded from *lok khed* as it imposed strict segregation by disallowing girls to participate.

Hussain Abbas of Model Town seemed worried by the extent of cultural dislocation suffered by society in modern times. He believes that cultural segregation has been imposed on Pakistani society. The media and other sources of manufacturing public opinion have persistently promoted values contrary to our cultural identity according to him. He states that it was after people of Pakistani origin came into physical contact with people of other nationalities (namely the Arabs during the 70's) which allowed our cultural fabric to be blemished.

Mushahid Masih a citizen of Lahore's Shadbagh area believes that *lok khed* was well embedded in our society until Partition came along. He recalls how his parents and grandparents lived in a society where a distinct set of cultural norms prevailed. He was of the view that partition dealt a severe blow to the cultural pluralism that existed in India. Partition according to him not only divided the country but also forced the various ethno-linguistic and religious groups into antagonizing one another. In doing so they wanted to differentiate their own cultures while refusing to take ownership of the values which they jointly upheld.

Ilhan Butt of Bari Gali seemed unhappy at the fact that *Lok Khed* did not receive the patronage of the government. He believes that *Lok Khed* could be instrumental in reinforcing a distinct South Asian identity, something which he believes is essential these days. He further stated that the country was involved in an existential crisis where it finds it difficult to define its own set of societal values. He believed that Western and Arab cultures had penetrated our society and suffered huge damage to our social fabric. He believed that our society had transformed into something entirely different from what it originally was.

Part II

Certain limitations were present in the study as the documentation of Punjabi folk games for their preservation remains an unexplored area which is the reason that the issues in discovering assets and references were experienced. For further studies, arranged visits to public libraries, conversations with social specialists and recording of more recreational folkgames are to be done. To realize the gap regarding the evolution and the archive of the following Punjabi folkgames, the documented events of interest have been analyzed.

Bandar Qilla

Bandar Qilla is a game that consists of individual players (no partners or teams). The opening player is determined by the historic custom "*pugan pugayee*". It's a type of toss that decides turns without the use of a coin. It's done by all players placing their hands in an open palm or on the back-hand side. The turn is decided when a person amongst all others, has an odd-facing hand. The person who remains last at *pugan pugayee* is considered the *Bandar* (Monkey - The loser). *Bandar* is the person who opens the game.

The game begins by tying a rope tightly with a large nail or a strong tree, wall or land if it could be fixed there. All players have to place their sandals or shoes as the game's sole equipment with the nail which is considered the *Qilla* (citadel) of the *Bandar* in the way to make a tower of the sandals. The person who is giving the turn needs to hold the rope tied with the nail and roam in circles around the *Qilla* to protect the tower made out of

shoes. All players have to run in trying to take the shoes away or break the tower and *Bandar* has to touch any one of the players. If a player is touched by the *Bandar* then the turn is shifted and that person becomes the *Bandar* and the game starts again from the beginning. If all shoes are taken out of the *Qilla* it's a nightmare for the *Bandar*. A point is already decided at the start of the game for the *Bandar* where they have to run in patterns for their life which is called *Hajj*. While the *Bandar* makes

his run after all the shoes are taken away all the players obstruct his movement by firing the shoes at him. *Bandar* is beaten up badly until he reaches the decided point and he is officially made a *Bandar*. *Bandar* is beaten throughout the run as the players wish and after this, the game starts again with the person as *Bandar* until that person catches someone else to change the shift.

Fig. 1, Video Still of Game “*Bandar Qilla*”

Gulli-Danda

A traditional game played all around South Asia with different variations to its names. Usually a team game, it can be played by any number of children. The rules are different everywhere and the players have the liberty to make their own rules.

Two wooden sticks are required for this game. *Gilli* - a small wooden piece 3-1/2 inches long 1-1/4 inches diameter at the center and tapering at both ends. *Danda* - a long stick two feet long and one inch in diameter, like a round ruler. A small circle of four feet in diameter is drawn on the ground. In the centre, a small oblong-shaped hole is dug which should be smaller than the *gilli*.

Two teams are formed. One bat and the other fields. Fielders stand in a position from where they can catch the *gilli*. The first player places the *gilli* in the hole and lifts it quickly high in the air with the *danda* and then strikes it. If he fails at first, he gets

another turn. If the fielder catches the *gilli* before it touches the ground, the batsman is out and the second player tries to hit the *gilli*. If the *gilli* is not caught, the distance from the hole to the place where the *gilli* falls is measured with the *danda*. Each *danda* equals one point.

The fielder stands where the *gilli* had fallen and tosses it to the batsman. The batsman tries to hit the *gilli* while it is in the air. If it falls, he taps the tapered end and lifts it in the air and strikes it while it is in the air. He gets three chances to hit the *gilli*. If he does not hit it or is caught, he is out. The game continues till all batsmen are out. The team changes sides and continues the same way. The team with a higher score wins. The game finds its relevance in Western games such as cricket and baseball but with easily available and accessible material rather than expensive gear such as bats and wickets.

Fig. 2, Video Still of Game “Gilli Danda”

Pittu Gol Garam (Seven Stones)

Seven Stones is a traditional Punjabi game, boasting a special place in the Punjabi Culture, and is still being played in most parts of its rural regions even today. It is also called *Lagori*, *saat-pathar* (seven stones), *pittu gol garam* and several other names, is the most complex popular children’s game in Lahore, and is rather like Dodge ball, but more aggressive. Two teams with an equal number of players need to be formed. A coin is tossed to select which team takes the attacking role first. Seven stones should be on top of each other as a pile within a circle and the defending team should take positions. The position for the fielding team will be wicketkeeper who will be behind the stones and other players around the stones randomly as fielders stand in cricket. All the players of the attacking team take position behind a crease line at an appropriate distance away from the pile of stones. The attacking team gets three chances to

hit the pile of stones with the ball (Underarm or Over arm) to knock the pile of stones. The attacking team has to hit the pile within three hits if they fail, then the defending and attacking team interchange places and continue to play, with one point for the formerly defending team if the attacking team has poor aiming skills. As soon as the ball knocks the pile of stones, the defenders catch hold of the ball and try to get the opposing players ‘out’ by hitting them with the ball in their leg below the knees (but the rule varies in different areas of Lahore). The attacking team aims to rearrange the pile of stones and trace the circle three times with their fingers before the other team can make all the players out. If they succeed in doing that, their team gets a point and they get the chance to throw the ball again. However, if all the players are out, then the defending team hits the stone and gains one point.

Fig. 3, Video Still of Game Pittu Gol Garam

Chug Chug

This game can be played with more than two players. In this game, kids make a circle with a stone or chalk and place their chickens between the circles. The game begins with a countdown from 5 to 1, each player with their chicken taps down their two fingers on the circle line and after the countdown begins they hit their fingers on the

ground hold as shown in Fig. 4 below with the sound of *Phaaah- Phaaah- Phaaah- Phaaah*. The player whose chicken leaves the circle loses the game and the team whose chicken stays in the circle wins. In old times, this game was used as a mode of betting.

Fig. 4, Video Still of Game Chug Chug

Gharmas / Kamas Ghori

This game is very popular among children in rural areas of Lahore. This game consists of two teams of 4-6 players on each side who form a line bending and grasping each other by the waist, the other side runs up as shown in Fig. 5 below and the main objective is to form a human ladder and one player has to climb higher than the opponent team on to the back of this ladder. The team

whose climber doesn't reach the height of the opposite team or the human ladder of one team falls is considered the losing team following a beating from the winning team. These games are orally transmitted, so over time, the name of this game has transformed from *gharmas ghori* to *ghori ghori* and the *kamas ghori*.

Fig. 5, Video Still of Game Gharmas Ghori / Kamas Ghori

Wanju Wanj or Body Body

It is one of the most popular games in the rural outskirts of Lahore. Some of the interviewees

mentioned that it originated from the time of crop cultivation when farmers and their families were done with the plantation. So the structure (grid)

of this game is derived from the pattern of the crop. In this game, children make a grid-like structure and divide themselves into two teams. And mark two points i.e. starting point A and ending point B. One team has to stay along with the grid and stop the other team from reaching the

end of point B. To stop a player from reaching the end, they have to touch or slap the other player. And the other team has to dodge the other players and reach the end. When all the players of one team cross the grid without being caught are declared winners.

Fig. 6, Video Still of Game Wanju Wanj

Oonch Neech

After a chain cut, a person is chosen as *Danner* or catcher. The playing members or the runners of the game can save themselves for a certain amount of time by stepping on *Oonch* which is a height (usually made of putting bricks on top of each other) or they can run on the lower level *Neech* which is the ground. The catcher chooses either *Oonch* (upper level) or *Neech* (lower level). Usually, the players who are chasing use *Neech*, to move as they are forbidden to step on *Oonch*. Once a runner steps on *Oonch*, the catcher cannot touch that

player by any means, and on the other hand, the catcher will try to catch anyone who steps off on the ground. If one of the runners stays on the ground by mistake and is captured by the catcher, then the person who is caught becomes the catcher in the next game. In the game, other players tease the catcher by saying "*Hum tumhari Neech pe or Hum tumhari Oonch pe*" which means "We're above you and you're below us" or in other words, "We're in your area, catch us".

Fig. 7, Video Still of Game Oonch Neech
 Lat'tu (Spinning Top)

This game has almost vanished from the rural landscape of Punjab. According to research with the discussion, the general public claims that *lat'tu* has been in existence for thousands of years. Like many traditional games, such as *kaenchay*, the earliest tops are made from clay and were discovered in the Middle East as early as 3500 BC, where children would likely have been spinning small rocks long before that. This game involves spinning a wooden toy called *la'tu* which is spherical at the top and tapered at the bottom. A string is wrapped around the top to spin it which is knotted at the end. The game is played through various methods and actions and mostly by young boys as girls rarely play it in public.

the players wind their tops with the rope attached to the bottom and then unwind it simultaneously after counting to three by releasing it from the

rope, throwing it on the ground to rotate for a few seconds, and then lifting it in the air, they try to catch it with the rope as quickly as possible. It depends on managing the shortest rope length which helps to rotate it and allowing one to catch it back with the rope. If the top fails to rotate on its nail on the ground – it is called 'Mittai', which means one loses the toss. If one fails to catch the top through the rope then one loses the toss as well. The last person to finish the 'toss' loses as well. The player who loses the toss will keep his top inside the boundary of the circle drawn on the ground. The rest of the players will have to attack on the top which is spinning inside the center of the circle. According to the public, another variation of this game includes a top that is spun on the palm of a person and then passed onto other players while spinning.

Fig. 8, Video Still of Game Lat'tu

Kabaddi

Kabaddi is one of the most popular games in South Asia which is also played as an official sport. It is played by two teams and each team has seven players on *Court*. Strength and power are put on display when a player surprise attacks the ones against the *Court*. The team spirit and secret strategies come into play when a person on the other side moves into the *Court*. The most important thing needed is stamina and the power of the lungs in order to be able to hold one's breath for a long time without any intervals. The group that wins the toss sends a Raider, who

moves against the group saying *kabaddi kabaddi* repeatedly in one breath. The purpose of the Raider is to touch at least one or more players of the opposite group and come back to the playing *Court* without losing his breath. The players of the opposite group who are touched by the Raider shall be disqualified by the Referee. The aim of the opposite team is to hold back the Raider till he loses his breath and stops saying *kabaddi kabaddi* in a rhythm. If the Raider fails to move into his *Court* in the same breath, he shall be declared out by the umpire or referee. Each group sends a player differently

into the ones against the court. If a player goes out of the division line during the direction of the play, or if any part of his body

touches the ground outside the division line, he will be eliminated.

Fig. 9, Video Still of Game Kabaddi

Kaenchay / Bantey / Marbles

Kaenchay is one of the most important games that is played in many parts of Lahore. It is also known as Marbles in English. This game is considered one of the hottest street games and it improves aiming and concentration skills. There are various ways of playing this game but the most played version found during this research is throwing the *kaenchay* into the hole. Each player contributes two or more marbles. The first player throws all the *bantey* aiming at the hole with one hand. If only two marbles or none of them fall in the hole,

then one of the other players chooses a marble, and the first player is asked to hit the selected marble with another marble that belongs to him. If he succeeds, he wins all the marbles in the hole. If not, he gets the one with which he hits. The next player takes his turn with the remaining marbles. If all the player's marbles do not go into the hole at the first, the second round starts. The players have to strike the marbles thrown by the other boys out of their way and try to push their marbles into the hole. The player who is left with the largest number of marbles is declared the winner.

Fig. 10, Video Still of Game Kaenchay

Kan Katori

In this game, players have to toss by using the same method of *pugan pugayee* to rule out the catcher. This game is played in an open space or a huge ground with more than six children. Once the catcher is selected through *pugan pugayee*, he has to

hold his left ear with his left hand and catch the other players with the sound *Cheeeeei* in a lower volume. This sound implies an airplane that will crash on the runners. The catcher now has to touch players one by one on the ground. The players will have to run constantly in the defined

area. As per the rule, the catcher cannot remove his hand from the left ear, otherwise, all the other players will beat him up. The player on getting caught joins the catcher and they hold each other's hand and become partners. The left hand on the

left ear is replaced by the hand of the new partner. The player who remains till the end has to run from one end to the other, if he successfully reaches there he becomes *Badshah* (King).

Fig. 11, Video Still of Game Kan Katori

Tapan Tapai

This is one of the most dangerous games found so far as shown in Fig. 12. It starts with the same method of '*pugan pugayee*' the player who loses the toss i.e. *pugan pugayee*, has to stand like a chair but bent from the upper torso and the rest of the

players have to jump over that person. The player who is in a bending position has to dodge the other players. If any of the players missed his jump and fell on the ground, he lost the game. As shown in Fig. 12.1

Fig. 12, 12.1, Video Stills of Game Tapan Tapai

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Phul Pati Badshah

This is one of the most played games among children in rural areas, especially in the streets. In this game, two players have to make different patterns with hands and legs for example a flower, mirror, vase, etc. as shown in Fig. 13 and the size

of each pattern increases after every turn or jump. The rest of the players have to cross over them or inside the shape without touching their bodies with their hands. This is one of the most subtle and peaceful games encountered in the study so far.

Fig. 13, Video Stills of Game “Phul Pati Badshah”

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

A sense of lost heritage and eroding culture was constantly in the views of all of those interviewed during the course of this research. The study found, through informal conversations with the interviewees that the society's negligent attitude towards their cultural values is considered the key factor in the gradual disappearance of *lok khed* from the socio-cultural landscape. This complex culture seems to have arisen as a result of our collective lack of interest in what is considered our “own” culture.

Among the various factors associated with this complex situation is the dominance of foreign culture(s) over our region. Being a post-colonial society, we have been strongly inclined towards embracing Anglo-Saxon values. Where our culture has developed a strong affinity with Western traditions, it has also been overpowered by it.

Lok khed eventually gave way to British games such as cricket, tennis, football, etc. as a result of colonization. One of the most influential factors in establishing the supremacy of Anglican games was the fact that they were more institutionalized compared to local Indian games which did not receive state patronage (unlike literature and the arts).

The invasion and successive adoption of foreign culture came at the cost of society's abandons of their cultural ideology which seemed to have been compromised. There seems to be a clear disharmony between local and foreign cultures which is observable with the decline of *lok khed*. Where *lok khed* worked towards establishing a distinct yet inclusive society, its gradual disappearance highlights societal differences to a greater degree. Epicurus, the Greek god of pleasure and the father of Hedonism preached that pleasure is an intrinsic value sought in the fulfillment of kinetic action. Epicurus propounded that the highest forms of pleasure are achieved in activities requiring bodily movement. The ancient Greeks are therefore said to have attached great significance to physical games and are considered to have fathered the modern sport.

In the modern age, the 18th-century English philosopher Jeremy Bentham laid huge emphasis on the role of pleasure in directing human life. He went on to state that "Nature has placed mankind under the governance of two sovereign masters, pain and pleasure".

Sigmund Freud later carried forward this theory when he described pleasure as the state achieved by suppressing or “detering gratification”. This is

what went on to be known as Freud's aggressive-release complex which he believed could be manifested in competitive sports.

Furthermore, French feminist philosophers Helene Cixous and Julia Kristeva attached sport to the social significance of pleasure. They hold the view that sport is the most socially acceptable means of achieving higher forms of physical pleasure.

The element of humor is deeply immersed in *Lok Khed*. The climax of *Bandar Qilla* for instance, requires the participants to show their aggression to the losing participant by hitting them with their sandals. In *Kamas/ Gharmas Ghori* similarly, the winning party makes a human tower on the loser(s) to emphasize their victory. What is clear from these practices is the popularity of a sense of comical humor where the victors make a visible display of their triumph by publicly embarrassing their opponents.

Being steeped in folk tradition, *lok khed* also reinforces cultural stereotypes associated with this region. Gender segregation is evident in the fact that women are mostly banned from participating in games that are exclusive to men and vice versa. The masculine, and to some extent, perverted nature of these games such as *gharmas ghori*, *wanju wanj* and *bandar qilla* abuses the participation of members of the opposite sex. Similarly, games such as *Khokla Chapaki*, *guriya guday ka khel* and *ouch neech* are fundamentally feminine and therefore disallow male participation.

The rapid urbanization witnessed in this region in the post-separation era of the Indian Sub-continent can also be characterized as a contributor to the decline of *lok khed*. The *mohalla* culture that existed earlier strongly declined and paved the way for a semi-urban environment that discouraged *lok khed*. The completeness of communities or *mohallas*, disintegrated as community habitation evolved. Unfortunately, Western sport was also commercialized and commoditized in this process. The gear and equipment used for *lok khed* failed to find the way in a society with a consumerist approach, where tennis rackets and hard balls were manufactured on an industrial scale.

Where the arts, music and literature flourished under the umbrella of state patronage during the Sikh, British and Post-Colonial periods, the local sports failed to find institutionalized support and never received attention from the state. During the British era, it was the sports favored by the British elite that made their way into the general public. In the years that followed, cricket which was characteristically a British invention and few shared traits with *Gilli Danda*, gained popularity. It was because of its singularity and widespread appeal that it was able to captivate the minds of a majority of the population. This resulted in a disinclined attitude towards local culture.

Oral history and personal accounts help us to establish that the *lok khed* tradition was once vibrant in our region. Its disappearance from the cultural and social landscape can be justified by society's preference for Western sports such as cricket, football and hockey. Furthermore, *Lok khed* is neither promoted by state machinery nor by popular media which can also be said to have resulted in its decline. However, its existence can still be felt in the urban ghettos and rural hinterlands of the country.

Intangible cultural heritage is what can be defined as peoples' knowledge and learning processes, the skills and creativity that are informed and developed by them, the products they create, the resources, spaces and other aspects of social and natural context necessary to their sustainability; these processes provide living communities with a sense of continuity with previous generations is important to cultural identity, and to the safeguarding of cultural diversity and creativity of humanity.

Furthermore, the archiving of the diminishing folk games has initiated several dialogues regarding the authorship of the documentation. Roland Barthes' article *Death of the Author* talks about the appreciation and the Author to Reader relationship. This claim also applies to visual arts i.e. artist-to-viewer relationship, which implies one must be able to appreciate or understand art regardless of prejudice or personal motivation. "The image of literature is centered on the author's personal life rather than the text or the work."

John Berger states “The camera isolated momentary appearances and in so doing destroyed the ideas that images were timeless. The invention of the camera changed the way men saw. The visible came to mean something different to them. This was immediately reflected in the painting.” Berger emphasizes how people's perspectives are constantly changing due to technology's intervention. An example is the camera, they can change the meaning and perspective of one's mind to view things differently. Each person has a different view however, having the image from the camera can reinforce the artist's vision and signify the diminishment of minor details. Berger's passage focuses on the change in people's views and how the change will continue as technology advances. The way individuals perceive art will vary from person to person.

“There's always something intriguing about a person I photograph.”

Steve McCurry, whose emotional images capture the essence of human struggle and joy, is recognized as one of today's finest photographers. The choice of location for documentation, the amount of time dedicated in a field and the candid shot quality that he delivers are commendable. Often accused of being stereotypical and exotic, the time that McCurry puts in the documentation of these controversial images, is most intriguing. The documentation of the games, people, children and the conversations that were recorded are the source of motivation to preserve and archive the intangible culture as well. However, the difference is that McCurry only shows one face of the story, which perhaps is also his strong suit. His most prominent work is *Afghan Girl (Sharbat Gula)* which was recognized worldwide and became a symbol of displaced people around the globe. She has been called the Third World's *Mona Lisa* and became even more popular when she was arrested in 2016 by Pakistani authorities for living there illegally. *Gula* was sentenced to fifteen days in detention and then deported to Afghanistan. The decision was criticized by Amnesty International. Similarly, Amar Kanwar's filmmaking practice challenges the limits of the medium in order to address the complex narratives about labor and locality rights, gender, religious fundamentalism

and ecology. He also works with documentary and archival images and employs various methods of editing and presentation to enhance the quality and essence, atmosphere, underlying meanings, and secretive histories. His works *The Trilogy: A Season Outside* (1997), *To Remember* (2003), and *A Night of Prophecy* (2002) focus on the relationship between Pakistan and India and the tension that has persisted between them since the partition. He talks about history which remains secretive and unmentioned to the general public. The parade at the *Wagah* border shows the aggression between the two nations. His work is somehow relevant to the study as it revisits the idea of history and explores its various layers/dimensions.

Ai Weiwei is a Beijing-based artist, and his practice ranges across filmmaking, photography, sculpture, performance, architecture, magazine publishing, curatorship, and, most provocatively. His work *Remembering*, a large-scale installation in Germany in 2009, inspect how improper material and lack of proper civil engineering led to the destruction of schools and claimed the lives of thousands of children trapped within them. He produced a list of all the earthquake victims on his blog. This act is typical of Weiwei's use of the internet to communicate information. This information is his “art”.

Weiwei tends to use art as a means of political activism, often through blogging and social media. His committed advocacy of free expression and human rights in China and abroad, and his criticism of the corruption and oppressiveness of the Chinese regime resulted in his arrest in 2011. He was put under intense surveillance and travel restrictions. From 1983–1993 he showcased a photographic installation which garnered wide appraisal.

Gayatri Spivak's article “Can the Subaltern Speak” talks about how Western culture investigates other cultures. The term ‘subaltern’ conventionally denotes an inferior military rank. She talks about the ethical problems of investigating a different culture on predefined i.e. universal concepts and frameworks. She also talks about how third-world subjects can be studied without cooperation with the colonial project. She points to the fact that

research is always colonial, in defining the 'other' i.e. the third world, the 'over there' subject as the object of study and as something that knowledge should be extracted from and brought back 'here' i.e. in the western world.

'Challenges of history writing in South Asia' is a book by Dr. Mubarak Ali, edited by Syed Jaffar Ahmad. This book is a compilation of articles from various researchers and educationists that majorly talk about how history has been abused in South Asia and treated as a stepchild. He talks about the denial of specific portions of history and the lack of access to Pakistani and Indian researchers on each other's archives.

Traced out extended themes

Raw examples of extended themes

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